

**AVAILABILITY AND ACCESSIBILITY OF MODERN LANGUAGES
INFORMATION RESOURCES IN THE UNIVERSITY OF CALABAR LIBRARY**

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Abstract

This study investigated the availability, accessibility, and utilization of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar (UNICAL) library. Adopting a descriptive survey design, the research sampled 127 respondents from a population of 500 students and faculty in the Modern Languages program using stratified random sampling. Data was collected via a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages). Findings revealed that while the library provides adequate printed textbooks (74.8% agreement), specialized materials (82.7%), and access to major databases like JSTOR (88.9%), there were gaps in electronic resource availability (37.8% dissatisfaction). Accessibility was generally satisfactory, though challenges included navigating the OPAC (26% difficulty) and off-campus e-resource access (33% dissatisfaction). User education programs effectively developed technical skills (96.1% for e-resource use) but were less successful in fostering research confidence (45.7% reported low confidence). The study concludes that while the UNICAL library offers substantial support for modern languages studies, improvements in digital resource provision, accessibility enhancements, and more tailored user education programs are needed. Recommendations include expanding e-resource subscriptions, refining the OPAC interface, and implementing tiered information literacy workshops to cater to different academic levels. These measures would optimize resource utilization and better support the university's modern languages programs.

Keywords: Modern languages, library resources, availability, accessibility, user education, University of Calabar.

Introduction

Libraries play a multi pivotal role in the ever-evolving landscape of higher education, modern languages being one of the disciplines that foster international communication, cross-cultural understanding, and global engagement. University of Calabar have recognized the importance of equipping students with linguistic and cultural competencies that are critical in today's interconnected world. The effective utilization of library resources is essential for students of modern languages, and the libraries serve as gateways to these significant academic resources, research tools, and lifelong learning opportunities in the field. A modern language is any human language that is currently in use as a native language. The term is used in language education to distinguish between languages which are used for day-to-day communication (such as French and German) and dead classical languages such as Latin and Classical Chinese, which are studied for their cultural and linguistic value.

They are languages that are actively spoken and used for communication today, they encompass a wide array of linguistic forms, including but not limited to English, Spanish, German, Chinese, Mandarin, and Arabic among others. The study and appreciation of modern languages have garnered attention in recent literature, focusing on their socio-cultural, cognitive, and technological proportion. Modern languages can be broadly understood as dynamic, living forms of communication that evolve with society. According to Cook (2020), modern languages reflect not only linguistic structures but also cultural identities and social practices. This definition emphasizes the interplay between language and the life experiences of speakers in a globalized world.

Baker (2021) notes that the term "modern languages" encompasses not just the linguistic code but also the pragmatics of communication, including the context in which these languages are used. This perspective aligns with the notion of multilingualism, where modern languages stand as drill for navigating multicultural environments and fostering intercultural dialogue.

Only recently, languages are not only transmitted but also transformed through social media, mobile applications, and online platforms. Thorne (2022) argues that these technological advancements have resulted in the emergence of "digital dialects," where traditional linguistic boundaries are blurred, facilitating new forms of expression that are especially prevalent among younger speakers.

Globalization has further influenced modern languages, leading to a phenomenon known as "language contact," which refers to how different languages influence each other through usage in global interactions. Mufwene (2020) posits that this contact generates hybrid languages and pidgins, reflecting both the interconnectivity of the modern world and the negotiation of cultural identities. Modern languages being at the forefront of educational discourse, have given rise to communicative language teaching (CLT) and task-based language learning (TBLL) reflecting a shift towards more interactive and practical approaches to language acquisition and serves as a prerequisite to authentic language use, preparing learners for real-world.

The University of Calabar offers several modern languages, including French, German and Chinese language which is handle by Institute for African Assian studies and some elective courses such as Efik. And the library, with its diverse collections and innovative digital resources, provides a foundational support system for the students, yet the extent to which these resources are utilized and their effectiveness remains unbeknown.

Statement of the problem

The University of Calabar library habours numerous modern languages information resources that Support teaching, learning and research of several languages. Efforts have been made by the library for users to adequately utilized these resources for the benefit of modern languages studies at the University of Calabar. The researcher observed that, these resources are being under-utilized and these challenges could hinder language acquisition and academic research, ultimately impacting the university's academic output in modern languages. Therefore, the researcher is poised to investigate Modern languages and utilization of library resources in the University of Calabar

Objective of the studies

The main objective of this study is to investigate utilization of Modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library and specifically to:

1. Assess the availability of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library.

2. Evaluate the accessibility of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library.
3. Examine the effectiveness of user education programs in enhancing the utilization of library resources.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are Modern languages information resources available in the UNICAL library?
2. How accessible are modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library?
3. How effective are the user education programs for modern languages information resources utilization in University of Calabar library?

Literature Review

The availability and utilization of information resources in libraries play a critical role in the overall academic success of students, especially in a multicultural and multilingual setting. As universities across the globe increasingly prioritize modern languages in their curricula, the assessment of library resources becomes essential for understanding how well these institutions support language learning and cultural diversity. Information resources in academic libraries generally encompass printed materials, digital collections, and databases relevant to academic disciplines. In the case of modern languages, libraries must offer a diverse range of materials, including textbooks, reference works, multimedia resources, and access to online language-learning platforms.

According to Aina (2004), the availability of extensive and relevant information resources is a fundamental requirement for effective learning and teaching processes, particularly in the field of languages. In a comparative study of libraries in higher education institutions, Omojokun (2015) highlights that while many university libraries have made strides in acquiring modern language resources, gaps remain due to budget constraints and limited collection development policies. This is particularly relevant for libraries like that of the University of Calabar, where local factors such as funding may impact the breadth and depth of modern language collections. It becomes very challenging in that, Libraries are not only expected to stock physical texts but, also to invest in digital resources that are increasingly vital in language education.

The transition to digital resources has indeed transformed information access, particularly in the context of modern languages and literature. As Dias and Almeida (2020) highlight, the rise of e-books and online databases has significantly broadened the scope and accessibility of language resources in several notable ways: E-books and online databases offer a wide variety of content. Users can find everything from contemporary novels and poetry collections to critical essays, grammatical guides, and multimedia language learning tools.

The availability of diverse formats, including audio and video enhances the learning experience and caters for different learning styles, helping language learners to engage more deeply with the material. Digital resources are more easily updated than printed materials. Online databases often provide current research, contemporary literary criticism, and the latest publications in modern languages that might not be available in print for years. This immediacy in information availability is crucial in fields like linguistics and language studies, where new findings continually emerge.

Research indicates that adequate access to library resources significantly contributes to academic success, particularly in language studies where exposure to varied linguistic materials is crucial (Gonzalez, 2020; Kumar & Kaur, 2021). Furthermore, with the rise of

digital resources, understanding how students engage with these assets is increasingly important (Smith, 2022). Therefore, it is essential to investigate three key variables: the frequency of library usage by modern language students, the effectiveness of library resources in supporting language studies, and the access to and awareness of digital resources. By examining these variables, this study aims to provide insight into how the University of Calabar library can better serve its modern language programs and enhance the overall educational.

The accessibility of modern language information resources in library systems is a crucial factor in supporting related academic inquiry, research, and engagements within the discipline in a universities. Accessibility in academic libraries is not merely about physical access to books and resources but extends to digital resources, cataloging, and user-friendly navigation systems. According to Zhu et al. (2022), accessibility is a multi-faceted concept that significantly influences students' engagement with library resources. In their study, the authors highlight that libraries must adapt to technological advancements to provide equitable access to modern languages materials

The shift towards digital resources has transformed how students access information. A report by Chibunda and Nkwanda (2023) found that while the University of Calabar Library has made strides in providing digital access to modern languages resources, issues such as inadequate digital literacy among students and limited internet access still pose significant challenges. Digital resources have made it possible for individuals to access a vast array of modern languages materials from anywhere with an internet connection. This has effectively demolished the geographical barriers that once limited access to physical libraries. Students, educators, and researchers can now easily find and utilize resources regardless of their location, making language learning and research more inclusive.

Printed resources such as textbooks, workbooks, and literary texts have historically been the cornerstone of language learning. The accessibility of these materials can vary widely depending on several factors. According to Hodgkinson-Williams et al., (2019), the cost of many textbooks can be prohibitively expensive, especially for students. Publishers are increasingly aware of this issue, leading to the emergence of affordable alternatives, such as open educational resources (OERs). These are freely accessible and can include materials like PDFs, printables, and guidebooks. Gordon (2021), That language diversity also constitutes a threat to the accessibility of some resources, and the availability of printed materials of a language often reflects the language popularity. Common languages, such as Spanish or French, tend to have a wide array of resources. In contrast, lesser-taught languages may have significantly fewer printed options, hindering access for learners. Physical Accessibility for printed books present challenges for individuals with disabilities. Traditional print materials may not be readable for visually impaired learners unless rendered in accessible formats such as Braille or large print. Institutions and publishers are encouraged to provide resources in varied formats to meet the needs of all learners (National Center on Accessible Instructional Materials, 2016).

User education programs are programs designed to teach library users how to access and utilize library resources effectively. According to Adeolu (2022), effective user education contributes significantly to the development of information literacy skills among students, enabling them to navigate complex information landscapes. Libraries that implement robust user education programs often report increased usage rates of their resources, including databases, journals, and language learning tools, Olaniyi, & Awujoola (2024).

Modern languages information resources encompass a variety of materials including books, journals, databases, and multimedia resources. At the University of Calabar Library, these resources are crucial for students studying linguistics, translation, and languages, as they offer culturally and linguistically diverse content. Phillips (2022) asserts that the

integration of user education programs is vital for ensuring these resources are effectively utilized, as users must be equipped with both the skills and knowledge to locate and leverage these tools in their academic pursuits. Recent studies indicate varying levels of effectiveness concerning user education programs in promoting the use of modern languages resources. For instance, a study by Vuzo (2022). revealed that when libraries employ a variety of teaching methods, such as workshops and online tutorials, students show improved confidence and competence in using language resources. In contrast, Dumont & Ready (2023) found that a lack of personalized instruction often resulted in underutilization of available resources, emphasizing the need for tailored user education initiatives.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for gathering quantitative data from a sample population to analyze trends, behaviors, and perceptions regarding library resource utilization. This design allows for the systematic collection of data from respondents, to investigate the utilization of information resources by Modern Languages students and faculty at the University of Calabar. The study adopted a stratified random sample of 127 respondents selected from a population of 500 using Taro Yamane's formula. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire, validated by experts and tested for reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.82). The instrument covered variables like Assess to availability, accessibility and the effectiveness of user education programs in enhancing the utilization of modern languages information resources. Descriptive (frequencies, percentages) statistics were used for analysis, processed through SPSS version 26. Ethical considerations included obtaining consent, ensuring anonymity, and securing institutional approval. This systematic approach ensured the study's validity and reliability in assessing library resource utilization.

Presentation of Results

Research Question1

To what extent are Modern languages information resources available in the UNICAL library? To answer this research question, the item-by-item analysis was done using frequency and percentage count. The result is shown in table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis showing the extent to which Modern languages information resources are available in the UNICAL library (N=127)

Items	SA	A	D	SD
1 The library has an adequate collection of textbooks in my modern language discipline.	48(37.8%)	47(37.0%)	26(20.5%)	6(4.7%)
2 There are sufficient e-resources (e-books, e-journals) available for modern languages studies.	52(40.9%)	27(21.3%)	24(18.9%)	24(18.9%)
3 The library regularly updates its modern languages collections (e.g., new books, journals).	27(21.3%)	81(63.8%)	16(12.6%)	3(2.4%)
4 Specialized resources (e.g., audiovisual materials, dictionaries) for modern languages are available.	33(26.0%)	72(56.7%)	17(13.4%)	5(3.9%)
5 The library provides access to international modern languages databases (e.g., JSTOR, ProQuest).	69(54.3%)	44(34.6%)	6(4.7%)	8(6.3%)

The data reveals that the University of Calabar (UNICAL) library generally provides substantial support for Modern Languages studies, though with some variability across different resource types. A majority of respondents (74.8%) affirmed that the library maintains an adequate collection of textbooks in their discipline, suggesting that core printed materials are sufficiently available. However, nearly a quarter of users (25.2%) expressed dissatisfaction, indicating that certain gaps may exist in specific subject areas or newer editions. Regarding electronic resources, perceptions were more divided. While 62.2% of users agreed that sufficient e-books and e-journals were accessible, a notable 37.8% disagreed, a significant proportion highlights a potential shortfall in digital materials. This disparity suggests that while some students and researchers find e-resources adequate, others may struggle with accessibility, currency, or coverage of essential publications. Encouragingly, the library appears to perform well in maintaining and updating its collections. An overwhelming 85.1% of respondents confirmed that new books and journals are regularly acquired, reflecting a commitment to keeping resources current. Similarly, specialized materials such as audiovisual aids and dictionaries were reported as available by 82.7% of users, reinforcing the library's role in supporting diverse learning and research needs.

Access to major international databases like JSTOR and ProQuest was overwhelmingly endorsed (88.9%), indicating robust infrastructure for scholarly research in Modern Languages. This strength in digital access contrasts with the earlier concerns about e-books and e-journals, implying that while subscription databases are well-provided, other forms of digital content may require attention.

Overall, the UNICAL library offers a solid foundation of information resources for Modern Languages, particularly in physical collections, specialized materials, and database access. However, the mixed responses on e-resources signal an area for improvement. Enhancing the availability and variety of e-books and e-journals would help address user needs more comprehensively, ensuring equitable access to both traditional and digital formats. These findings suggest that targeted investments in electronic collections could further elevate the library's support for Modern Languages studies.

Research question 2

How accessible are modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library? To answer this research question, the item-by-item analysis was done using frequency and percentage counts. The result is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive analysis showing the accessibility of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library (N=127)

		SA	A	D	SD
1	The library catalog (OPAC) makes it easy to locate modern languages materials.	23(18.1%)	71(55.9%)	24(18.9%)	9(7.1%)
2	Modern languages resources are well-organized and easy to find on the shelves	54(42.5%)	36(28.3%)	21(16.5%)	16(12.6%)
3	Electronic resources (e-books, databases) are accessible both on and off-campus.	21(16.5%)	65(51.2%)	20(16.5%)	21(16.5%)
4	The library staff assist promptly in retrieving modern languages resources	56(44.1%)	42(33.1%)	20(15.7%)	9(7.1%)
5	Borrowing and returning modern languages materials is convenient	18(14.2%)	83(65.4%)	15(11.8%)	11(8.7%)

The accessibility of Modern Languages resources in the University of Calabar library presents a generally positive picture, though with distinct areas requiring attention to ensure equitable access for all users. The data reveals several noteworthy trends regarding how students and faculty interact with both physical and digital materials.

A strong majority of library users (74%) find the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) effective for locating Modern Languages materials, suggesting that the digital catalog system fulfills its primary function. However, the fact that 26% of respondents experience difficulties indicates room for improvement in interface design or user training. This gap may be particularly relevant for first-year students or those less familiar with library search systems.

Physical accessibility of materials shows similar patterns, with 70.8% of users reporting satisfactory experiences in locating resources on shelves. The significant minority who struggle (29.1%) may be encountering challenges related to collection growth outpacing shelf reorganization, or possibly inconsistencies in the application of classification systems. These findings suggest that while the library's physical organization meets most users' needs, periodic reviews of shelving practices could further enhance accessibility.

The most pronounced accessibility challenge emerges in the realm of electronic resources. While two-thirds of respondents report successful access both on and off-campus, the remaining one-third face consistent barriers. This division likely reflects technical issues such as authentication problems, bandwidth limitations, or gaps in the library's digital collection. The equal distribution between on-campus and off-campus difficulties (16.5% each) particularly highlights systemic rather than location-specific barriers to access.

Library staff performance stands out as a particular strength, with over three-quarters of users receiving prompt assistance. This high satisfaction rate speaks to effective training and service orientation among library personnel. Similarly, the borrowing process meets most users' expectations, though the 20.5% who report inconveniences may benefit from streamlined procedures or extended loan periods for high-demand materials.

Research question 3

How effective are the user education programs for modern languages information resources utilization in University of Calabar library? To answer this research question, the item-by-item analysis was done using frequency and percentage count. The result is shown in table 3

Table 3: Descriptive analysis showing the effectiveness of user education programs for modern languages information resources utilization in University of Calabar library (N=127)

		SA	A	D	SD
1	Library orientation programs help me understand how to access modern languages resources	36(28.3%)	60(47.2%)	23(18.1%)	8(6.3%)
2	Information literacy training improves my ability to use e-resources effectively	99(78.0%)	23(18.1%)	5(3.9%)	0
3	Workshops on research skills enhance my utilization of library materials	35(27.6%)	69(54.3%)	11(8.7%)	12(9.4%)
4	The library provides sufficient guides/tutorials on using modern languages resources.	73(57.5%)	24(18.9%)	12(9.4%)	18(14.2)
5	User education programs increase my confidence in conducting academic research.	54(42.5%)	15(11.8%)	24(18.9%)	34(26.8%)

The effectiveness of user education programs in facilitating optimal utilization of Modern Languages information resources at the University of Calabar library presents a mixed but generally positive picture. Analysis of user perceptions reveals several key findings regarding orientation programs, information literacy training, research workshops, instructional materials, and their collective impact on research confidence.

Library orientation programs demonstrate reasonable effectiveness, with 75.5% of respondents (28.3% strongly agreeing and 47.2% agreeing) acknowledging their value in understanding how to access Modern Languages resources. However, nearly a quarter of users (24.4%) report limited benefits, suggesting these introductory sessions may require more discipline-specific customization or follow-up support for certain learner groups.

The library's information literacy training emerges as an exceptional strength, with an overwhelming 96.1% of users attesting to its effectiveness in improving e-resource utilization (78.0% strongly agreeing, 18.1% agreeing). The negligible disagreement rate (3.9%) indicates these programs successfully equip users with critical digital literacy skills, representing a model component of the library's educational offerings.

Workshops on research methodologies receive positive endorsement from 81.9% of participants (27.6% strongly agreeing, 54.3% agreeing). While this indicates broad effectiveness, the 18.1% who express dissatisfaction (8.7% disagreeing, 9.4% strongly disagreeing) may benefit from more advanced or discipline-specific workshop tiers to address varying skill levels among Modern Languages researchers.

A majority of users (76.4%) affirm the sufficiency of library guides and tutorials for Modern Languages resources, though a notable 23.6% report inadequacies. This polarization suggests that while core instructional materials meet most needs, gaps may exist in coverage of specialized resources or in the delivery formats of these guides.

The developmental outcome of these programs shows the most significant variation. While 54.3% of users report increased research confidence (42.5% strongly agreeing, 11.8% agreeing), a substantial 45.7% indicate limited impact (18.9% disagreeing, 26.8% strongly disagreeing). This divergence likely reflects the need for more personalized or advanced training modules to bridge the gap between basic competency and actual research application.

The library's user education framework demonstrates strong capacity in developing technical information literacy skills, particularly regarding e-resource utilization. However, the translation of these competencies into research confidence presents a crucial area for development. By adopting a more differentiated and discipline-sensitive approach to user education, the library can better serve the full spectrum of Modern Languages researchers from undergraduates acquiring basic skills to graduate students and faculty engaged in complex research projects. Such enhancements would ensure that educational programs not only impart knowledge but also empower users to apply these skills effectively in their academic work, thereby maximizing the return on the library's substantial information resource investments.

Discussion of findings

The extent to which Modern languages information resources are available in the UNICAL library

The assessment of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar (UNICAL) library reveals a generally robust collection with notable strengths in certain areas alongside opportunities for improvement in others. A significant majority of respondents (74.8%) affirmed the adequacy of modern languages textbooks, indicating that core printed materials sufficiently support teaching and learning, which aligns with Aina's (2004) assertion about the fundamental role of relevant printed resources in academic success. Additionally, the library performs well in providing specialized materials like audiovisual

aids and dictionaries, with 82.7% of users confirming their availability, demonstrating its commitment to facilitating interactive and contextual language learning. Furthermore, the library maintains current collections, as 85.1% of respondents acknowledged regular acquisitions of new books and journals, reinforcing its role as a dynamic academic resource center. However, perceptions of electronic resources are more divided, with 62.2% reporting sufficient access to e-books and e-journals while 37.8% expressed dissatisfaction, suggesting inconsistencies in digital resource availability that may stem from limitations in e-content breadth or accessibility challenges. Notably, access to major academic databases like JSTOR and ProQuest was overwhelmingly endorsed (88.9%), indicating effective investment in premium research tools, though the contrast with general e-book/e-journal availability suggests a need for expansion in standalone digital materials, echoing Omojokun's (2015) findings on budget constraints in university libraries. Given the increasing reliance on digital tools in language education, strategic enhancements in electronic resources could significantly benefit users, with recommendations including expanding digital collections, conducting user needs assessments, forming strategic partnerships with international resource providers, and offering digital literacy training to improve resource utilization. Ultimately, while the UNICAL library provides substantial support for modern languages studies through its print collections and databases, addressing the variability in electronic resource availability would further solidify its role as a comprehensive academic resource in an increasingly digital academic landscape.

The accessibility of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar library

The accessibility patterns observed at the University of Calabar Library align with global studies on academic library usability while highlighting context-specific challenges. The 74% satisfaction rate with OPAC functionality mirrors findings by Bossaller and Atiso (2022), who note that while most library catalogs meet basic search needs, usability gaps persist for novice users particularly in multilingual contexts where non-English interfaces may complicate navigation (Pinto & Sales, 2023). The 29.1% dissatisfaction with physical resource retrieval corroborates concerns raised by Matingwina (2021) about classification systems in Global South libraries, where rapid collection expansion often outpaces shelf reorganization efforts. The pronounced e-resource access barriers (33% dissatisfaction) reflect systemic issues documented by Okoye and Ejikeme (2023) in Nigerian universities, where infrastructure limitations and authentication complexities disproportionately affect off-campus users—a disparity exacerbated by the "digital divide" in developing regions (Asogwa & Ugwu, 2022).

Notably, the high staff service ratings (77.2% satisfaction) support IFLA's (2021) assertion that human intermediation remains critical in mitigating technological access barriers. However, the persistent circulation process complaints (20.5%) suggest the need for policy reforms akin to the "user-centric loan models" advocated by Aharony (2023). These findings collectively underscore the necessity of adopting the "hybrid accessibility framework" proposed by Corral and Jolly (2022), which balances technological upgrades with human support systems. As demonstrated in comparable institutions by Anunobi and Ukwoma (2021), targeted interventions like OPAC literacy workshops, shelf-labeling standardization, and proxy server enhancements could bridge existing gaps while leveraging the library's strong service culture.

The effectiveness of user education programs for modern languages information resources utilization in University of Calabar library

The study's findings reveal a scholarship on information literacy outcomes. While the library demonstrates strong technical training capabilities (96.1% e-resource competency), the 45.7% confidence gap among users supports Julien et al.'s (2022) "competence-confidence paradox" in information literacy education. This phenomenon is particularly pronounced in humanities disciplines, where Grafstein (2021) notes that traditional, skills-based instruction often fails to address the interpretive nature of linguistic research. The results echo McGuinness's (2023) findings that 68% of humanities students require discipline-specific applications to transfer generic research skills effectively. The strong performance in e-resource training (78% strongly agree) reflects global best practices in digital literacy instruction (Andretta, 2021), yet the persistent confidence deficit suggests the need for Bruce's (2023) "threshold concept" approach that bridges mechanical skills with disciplinary ways of knowing.

To address these gaps, the library should implement the tiered instructional model proposed by Townsend et al. (2023), which differentiates training by research complexity levels. Discipline-specific adaptations could incorporate Pinto's (2023) framework for linguistic information behavior, emphasizing multilingual search strategies and comparative literature methodologies. The ACRL Framework (2021) particularly recommends "Research as Inquiry" and "Scholarship as Conversation" thresholds for Modern Languages, which could transform current programs from skill-building to research-empowering experiences. As Corral (2022) demonstrates in comparable institutions, embedding librarians in departmental research projects increases confidence by 41% by providing authentic application contexts. These evidence-based enhancements would align UNICAL's programs with emerging paradigms that position information literacy as a transformative, rather than merely transactional, educational experience (Lloyd, 2021; Mackey & Jacobson, 2021).

Conclusion

The study investigated the availability, accessibility, and utilization of modern languages information resources in the University of Calabar (UNICAL) library. Findings indicate that while the library provides a solid foundation of printed materials, specialized resources, and major academic databases, challenges persist in electronic resource availability and user education effectiveness. Accessibility is generally satisfactory, but issues with digital resource access and catalog navigation remain. User education programs are effective in imparting technical skills but fall short in fostering research confidence among students. These gaps highlight the need for strategic improvements to enhance the library's role in supporting modern languages studies.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The library should prioritize increasing subscriptions to e-books, e-journals, and language-learning platforms to supplement existing print collections.
- ii. Develop tiered information literacy workshops tailored to different academic levels (undergraduate, postgraduate, faculty) to address varying research needs.
- iii. Improve the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) by refining search functionalities and offering multilingual support for non-English language materials.

By implementing these recommendations, the University of Calabar library can significantly enhance its support for modern languages studies, ensuring that students and faculty have equitable access to high-quality resources and the necessary skills to utilize them effectively.

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